

THE IMPORTANCE OF FINE ARTS IN DEVELOPING THE CREATIVITY OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract: Scientific data on the formation and development of visual and artistic creativity of primary school students in visual arts classes and a proposal for the organization of visual arts lessons in primary grades have been combined. and opinions are expressed.

Keywords: formation of a positive and creative attitude towards the subject of visual arts, creativity, ability and potential, educational competencies related to visual literacy, visual and artistic-creative thinking, visual creativity qualities.

In our country today, on the basis of the further improvement of the primary education system, it is necessary to raise a healthy and fully mature, well-rounded generation, to realize the fine artistic skills of students and young people related to visual arts the further development of an effective system of fundamental improvement of the quality of teaching through the widespread introduction of modern information communication and advanced pedagogical technologies, including electronic textbooks, multimedia tools, etc., in the educational processes conducted in art, becomes urgent.

What is creativity? What is the process? What does it mean? Creativity can be considered as a qualitatively new process resulting from human activity that creates material and spiritual wealth. Creativity represents the unique ability of a person that is manifested behind the work he does [4]. On the basis of knowledge of the laws of the objective world, there can be work, creativity that creates a new reality that satisfies various social needs. There are many types of creativity and they are determined by creative activity: inventor, organizer, scientific, visual and artistic work, etc. The opportunities that need to be created for creative activity depend on social relations. Today's educational reforms are carried out depending on the training of qualified personnel with high knowledge and potential, who have a creative approach to their work, who make their due contribution to the rapid development of science, technology, art, and production. increases. Accordingly, it is very important and necessary to educate every student in the spirit of creativity, based on the students of social development. After all, students with different potentials and abilities are educated in general secondary education schools, finding such abilities and potentials in students and developing them gradually is the first task of general secondary education school teachers. is the task of the gal.

Therefore, in order to achieve the main goal of primary education, that is, to form a positive and creative attitude to the subject of visual arts in primary school students, to develop educational competencies related to visual literacy. creating content, teaching students to work with various visual tools (pen, watercolor, gouache, felt-tip pen, dream, etc.) , it is necessary to pay special attention to the formation of visual and artistic-creative

thinking in them, to teach them to draw freely in visual and practical activities, and to implement high-quality educational activities.

A unique approach to them is also of great importance in the development of creative and practical activities related to visual arts in elementary school students [5]. It is known that every elementary school student is unique [6]. The uniqueness of a person is determined by the characteristics of his psyche, which is formed under the influence of various individual and social development factors [7].

In our opinion, the creativity of a primary school student in visual arts is the ability to literately and skilfully apply the acquired theoretical knowledge in visual and practical activities, accurately and objectively evaluate the obtained and achieved results, carefully analyze them, is to be able to generalize the results with a new one.

The teacher of fine arts must pay attention to two interrelated tasks in order to effectively organize students' creative activities related to the field during the training:

the first - with the development of independent thinking of elementary school students in the creative activity of visual arts, their eagerness to acquire knowledge, the realization of their drawing ability and talent, and the formation of their scientific and artistic-visual outlook;

the second is determined by teaching to independently apply acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities in education and visual practical activities.

As a conclusion, it can be said that, based on the opinions expressed, it is possible to consistently train elementary school students for visual creativity in relation to visual arts in the following directions:

- it is necessary to draw the attention of elementary school students to the universality and comprehensiveness of the method used in solving the assigned task;
- it is necessary to achieve that the teaching of visual creativity of elementary school students is considered not as the goal of the lesson, but as a new way and opportunity aimed at more effectively solving the task set in the lesson;
- it should be considered as the main product of classes of visual creativity with new ideas and content that primary school students draw their own conclusions;
- collection of new information and data, their analysis and interpretation should be considered as an important aspect of creating creativity in visual arts;
- to consider the formation and education of the qualities of visual creativity in the personality of a primary school student not only as an important part of the activities carried out in general secondary schools, in terms of their scope, but also outside the school. It is also important to consider it as a matter.

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